

Optimization of anisotropic cylinders with manufacturing tolerances in tow placement accounted for

P.Y. Tabakov* and M. Walker

Center for Advanced Materials, Design & Manufacture Research
Durban University of Technology, PO Box 1334, Durban 4000, South Africa

SUMMARY

The present study provides a technique for determining the optimal design of anisotropic laminated pressure vessels. The vessels are fabricated via tow placement, and the tolerances are due to deviations between the design and actual tow orientations after placement. It is also assumed that the deviation varies throughout the orientation interval and that the variation curve resembles a bell-curve.

Keywords: *manufacturing tolerance, composite structures, optimal design*

INTRODUCTION

There is an increasingly large effort being made to determine methods that can account for uncertainty in design and yield optimized designs. Robust Design Optimization (RDO) is intended to yield a system that performs with minimal variability in the face of input variations or uncertainties. RDO methods generally seek to minimize the variation of an Aggregate Objective Function (AOF) and to maintain design feasibility under input variations. The optimization outcome depends on the acceptable level of variations in performance, and also on the level of input variations [1]. Robust design, thus, is an approach that explicitly recognizes the effects of these variations and seeks to minimize their consequences, without eliminating their sources.

Various researchers have used robust optimization techniques in the design optimization of structures. Generally, because most of these design problems are multi-dimensional, the solution techniques have multiple steps, and nested approaches are necessary. These are computationally expensive, but convex methods are popular. In [2], the problem of optimally designing composite plates under uncertain in-plane loading conditions is considered. A minimax formulation is proposed and demonstrated, and the buckling load is maximized with respect to the structural parameters and minimized with respect to variations in the load parameters. The admissible loading configurations belong to a convex hull which significantly enhances the optimization procedure. In [3], the layup optimization of laminated composites with free edges is considered. The objective is maximum strength, and genetic algorithms (GAs) are used. In the formulation of the GA, a repair strategy was adopted to satisfy given constraints. Multiple elitism schemes were implemented to efficiently find

*Corresponding author. Email: pashat@dut.ac.za

multiple global optima or near optima. A convex modeling technique is proposed to consider the bounded uncertainty of material properties.

Another popular trend for dealing with uncertainty is the use of probabilistic methods. Tonon and Bernardini [4] consider the optimization of structures whose parameters are assigned as fuzzy numbers or fuzzy relations as a particular case of the random set theory and evidence theory approach. Two numerical examples are used to illustrate the methodology that is presented. In [5], the process of optimum design of structures is developed in which design parameters with a fuzzy nature are considered. The fuzzy optimum problem is transformed into an ordinary unconstrained optimum problem by expressing the objective function in the form of fuzzy expected cost. Illustrative numerical examples are presented and a comparison between various cases for both system failure cost and fuzziness of design parameters is performed.

Various other miscellaneous methods have been reported in the scientific press. For example, Sangren [6] uses a nonlinear goal programming formulation which allows for multiple design objectives as well as hard and soft constraints to design a three-bar truss, whilst topological changes in the design are achieved using design sensitivities. Lombardi and Haftka [7] design for uncertainty in load using a worst-case-scenario technique of anti-optimization. To solve the resulting nested optimization problem, the methodology described in the paper alternates between optimization and anti-optimization to alleviate the computational burden, and is applied to the design of a simply supported laminated composite and other straightforward structures. Adali *et al.* [8] consider the optimal design of composite laminates under buckling load uncertainty. The laminates are subjected to biaxial compressive loads and the buckling load is maximized under worst case in-plane loading which is computed using an anti-optimization approach. Results are given for continuous and discrete fibre orientations which constitute an optimization problem coupled to a load anti-optimization problem leading to a nested solution method. It was found that the buckling load carried by a deterministic design is considerably less than the one carried by a robust design when both are subjected to uncertain loads.

In [9], the population of design candidates has been exploited to provide samples for evaluation of uncertain functions in an effort to perform optimization under uncertainty with a reasonable amount of computational effort. A simple three-bar truss problem is used as an example, and designs were generated using GAs with population-based sampling. Results generated compared favorably with a design generated using a deterministic approach with safety factors and designs generated using a GA with Monte Carlo evaluations to estimate probabilities. Lee *et al.* [10] describe a robust design methodology developed to obtain an optimum value insensitive to variations in design variables within a feasible region. This is performed by using a mathematical programming algorithm. A multiobjective function is defined to have the mean and the standard deviation of the original objective function, while the constraints are supplemented by adding a penalty term to the original constraints. This method has an advantage in that the second derivatives of the constraints are not required, and several standard problems for structural optimization are solved to illustrate it.

A few researchers have described methods for dealing with manufacturing tolerances. For example, Bauer and Latalski [11] consider the issue of manufacturing tolerances in dimensions with regard design optimization, when the objective is minimum weight. A standard solution algorithm with the Kuhn-Tucker theorem is used with the adjoined variable method, and the method is illustrated using the standard ten bar bench-mark problem; typical for testing algorithms in structural optimization.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The design optimisation of anisotropic laminated cylinders used as pressure vessels fabricated using the tow placement method is considered here and the mathematical solution implemented is based on an exact three-dimensional elasticity solution. For the sake of simplicity only single and two layered vessels of two different thickness ratios have been used as examples.

The approach used in this study is based on the research findings published in [12]. That study provides an in-depth analysis of the multi-dimensional problem and then a technique for determining the optimal design of engineering structures, with manufacturing tolerances in the design variables accounted for. It was assumed previously that the probability of any tolerance value occurring within the tolerance band, compared with any other, was equal, and thus it was a worst-case scenario approach. However, in the tow placement process, the deviation of the fibres from the intended design paths during fabrication depends on the angle of placement required. The amount of deviation can usually be approximately described by a sine-cosine curve. Although the particular characteristics of this curve will vary from one tow placement machine to another, a very good approximation can be achieved by varying particular parameters.

To illustrate the technique, the *maximum* lower and upper tolerances (or deviations), positive and negative, are assumed to be $T_l = \theta - 13^\circ$ and $T_u = \theta + 13^\circ$ (Case 1) and $T_l = \theta - 11^\circ$ and $T_u = \theta + 11^\circ$ (Case 2).

The sine-cosine curve is described by the following expression (on the interval $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$):

$$T(\theta) = \begin{cases} T_l \left(1 - \sin \frac{\pi\theta}{2\mu} \right) & \forall \quad 0^\circ \leq \theta \leq \mu \\ \frac{1}{2}T_u \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi(\theta - \mu)}{\eta - \mu} \right) & \forall \quad \mu \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In the above equation the variable $T(\theta)$ is the tolerance, μ is the mean value where the tolerance is equal to zero, and η is the point where the tolerance reaches its maximum. We considered two cases of the mean value, namely $\mu = 30^\circ$ (Case 1) and $\mu = 40^\circ$ (Case 2) and these are shown graphically in Figure 1.

The simplest example is a one-dimensional optimization problem. Determining the global optimum, even accounting for the manufacturing tolerances, does not present any difficulties. In many cases a fast and accurate direct calculation is sufficient. In the case when high accuracy of the design parameter is required the problem can be

Figure 1: Sine-cosine tolerance curves.

stated as follows

$$F_{max} \vee F_{min} = \max \vee \min \varphi(x) \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi(x)$ is an artificial asymptotic function. Assuming that the function describing the behaviour of an engineering structure is continuous and smooth and should any anomalies be presented they are known and predictable, it can be written as

$$\varphi(x) = \frac{1}{B^{\alpha d}} \cdot (f^{(u)}(x) \vee f^{(l)}(x)) \quad (3)$$

where B is an empirical value (the bigger the number the more pronounced the asymptotic behaviour of the function); d is a difference between the two functions (upper and lower tolerance functions); α is an adjustment coefficient which helps to avoid very large numbers in the exponent; and $f^{(u)}(x)$ and $f^{(l)}(x)$ represent upper and lower tolerance functions, respectively. The fraction in the above expression will be equal to one when the intersection occurs and approach zero as the function lines separate from each other.

Alternatively, if both the values of $f^{(u)}(x)$ and $f^{(l)}(x)$ are of the same sign, i.e. both positive or negative, such function can be stated as follows

$$\varphi(x) = \left(1 - \frac{|f^{(u)}(x) - f^{(l)}(x)|}{|f^{(u)}(x) + f^{(l)}(x)|} \right) \cdot (f^{(u)}(x) \vee f^{(l)}(x)) \quad (4)$$

The range of the expression in the brackets is on the interval $[1, 0]$, which means that it equals one if the two functions intersect and approaches zero if they are far apart. The advantage of the above approach is the absence of empirical values while its shortcoming is a loss of accuracy when the objective function has a rather steep

gradient. Contrary to it, it is apparent that the former case (3) is universal and can be applied to any valid pair of functions. The drawback only is the necessity of choosing the empirical values B and α . Theoretically, both the methods can be applied to any valid pair of multimodal functions; however, a multiple number of the functional (hyper-)surfaces will create an impenetrable barrier for optimization.

When analyzing multidimensional problems we must check all the possible combinations of deviations from the intended design which can take place during the manufacturing process and choose the worst possible scenario. For example, if the structure has two design parameters, then there are four such combinations plus the nominal case (viz. tolerance equal to 0). This means that for every iteration of the algorithm the objective function must be calculated five times. Respectively, for N dimensions we have $2^N + 1$ possible scenarios to check. As the dimensionality increases, it might be more productive to employ the nesting optimization technique, which means that when calculating the objective function, we call another optimization procedure.

While any suitable optimization technique can be used for the main part of the problem, for the nested part hardly anything else is better suited than the micro-genetic algorithm (μ GA) [13]. This is because we deal with a very simple combinatorial problem. When correctly applied, the algorithm is very fast and efficient and thus destroys the myth of the inconceivable complexity of nesting optimization. Since the μ GA is a relatively new technique and not widely used yet, we shall give next a short outline of it.

The μ GA operates on a family, or population, of design individuals similar to the standard genetic algorithm. However, unlike the GA, a very small population size (usually five) is used. The fitness of each individual is calculated and the fittest individual is carried to the next generation (viz. elitist strategy). The parents of the remaining four individuals are determined using a tournament selection strategy. In this strategy, individuals are paired randomly and adjacent pairs compete to become parents of the remaining four individuals in the following generation [13]. Convergence of the μ -population is checked and a new random population is chosen and the evolution process restarts. In our case, population convergence occurs when the difference in bits of the chromosome between the best and other individuals is less than 5%. If the population has not converged, then the evolution process does not restart. In addition, mutation is not applied in the μ GA since enough diversity is introduced after convergence of a μ -population. By using the techniques described above, the following numerical examples demonstrate the impact of the manufacturing tolerance on the overall performance of some fibre-reinforced laminated structures.

EXAMPLE RESULTS

As mentioned, for simplicity and for the purposes of visual illustration, we study vessels with one and two layers as examples, but the approach used is the same for any number of design parameters (layers) except that the nesting algorithm should be used for higher dimensions. The material properties are those for a typical T300/5208 graphite/epoxy material: $E_1 = 1.811 \times 10^5$ MPa, $E_2 = 1.03 \times 10^4$ MPa, $G_{12} = 7.17 \times 10^3$ MPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.2897$. The ratio of the external radius to internal in the

cylinder used in the examples is either $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.01$ (thin) or $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.1$ (thick), while the length is arbitrary. The reinforcement used is angle-ply forming orthotropic layers in cylindrical coordinates. The analysis used is an exact three-dimensional elasticity solution which takes also into account the effect of closed ends (see Figure 2). Unfortunately, the mathematical foundations of the analysis are quite cumbersome and thus cannot be accommodated here. The interested reader can find the detailed solution in [12] or should contact the authors.

Figure 2: Geometry of an anisotropic cylindrical pressure vessel.

Using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion [14] we attempt to calculate the maximum burst pressure with respect to the fibre orientations in the layers and taking into account the manufacturing tolerances. Generally, the problem can be stated as follows

$$\max P_{cr} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max_{\theta} \min_R P_{cr}(\theta, R) \quad (5)$$

Figure 3 clearly demonstrates how dangerous the manufacturing tolerances can be should they occur during the manufacture of a pressure vessel if the design has not accounted for them. The results are for a vessel with one layer, $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.01$ and the first tolerance case (as represented in Figure 1). Although fractions of degrees usually are not taken into account by the manufacture, for academic purposes we calculated the exact value of the maximum critical pressure (nominal case) as $P_{cr} = 4.49\text{MPa}$ at $\theta = 54.22^\circ$. It can be seen from the figure how sensitive the burst pressure is to the change in the fibre orientation. When the tolerances (both upper and lower) are accounted for we discover that the actual value of the burst pressure drops from the nominal one by 46.5% to 2.40MPa (the value given by the intersection of the upper and lower tolerance curves). Furthermore, if we were to specify the nominal value of the orientation and yet during fabrication tolerances were incurred, the burst pressure could be as low as 2.32MPa (at $54.22 - 3.65^\circ$), which is 48% lower than the expected (nominal) value.

Figure 4 shows the three trend lines for the thick cylinder with $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.1$ (and tolerance Case 1). The nominal critical burst pressure is 47.90MPa for $\theta = 54.45^\circ$ and the actual is 24.83MPa (or 48% less) for $\theta = 54.12^\circ$.

When we study vessels with two layers and tolerance Case 1 applied to the first layer and Case 2 to the second, we see the effect of the tolerances is less severe than in the single layer cases. Figure 5 shows the results for the thin cylinder and here the

nominal burst pressure is 3.13MPa at $\theta_1 = 41.09^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 64.92^\circ$, whilst the actual critical pressure is 2.76MPa (viz. 12% less) at $\theta_1 = 69.36^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 37.28^\circ$. The results for the thick cylinder with two layers are shown in Figure 6. These examples clearly demonstrates how important it is to take the manufacturing tolerances into account in the design optimization stage. They also illustrates that is much safer to use a few layers instead of one. However, calculations show that after 10 layers there is not much improvement in the performance of the pressure vessel.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a generalized technique for optimally designing engineering structures with manufacturing tolerances in the design variables is presented. It is assumed that there can be an upper and lower tolerance in each case, and thus for a problem with N dimensions, it is demonstrated that the solution lies within the common domain of the $2^N + 1$ possible hyper-surfaces. Furthermore, it is also assumed that the probability of any tolerance value occurring within the tolerance band, compared with any other, is equal, and thus it is a worst-case scenario approach. In order to determine the optimum solution, the technique utilizes a genetic algorithm with fitness sharing, including a micro-genetic algorithm, which has been found to be very suitable (viz. accurate, fast and efficient), particularly when the dimensionality of the problem is high.

In order to demonstrate the technique, the design optimisation of anisotropic laminated cylinders used as pressure vessels fabricated using the tow placement method are considered and the mathematical solution implemented is based on an exact three-dimensional elasticity solution. The vessels are fabricated via tow placement, and the tolerances are due to deviations between the design and actual tow orientations after placement. It is also assumed that the deviation varies throughout the orientation interval. The importance of accounting for the tolerances during design optimisation is demonstrated by comparing the optimal designs of both thin and thick vessels when the tolerances have been included (actual) and ignored (nominal) in the optimisation stage.

For the sake of simplicity only single and two layered vessels of two different thickness ratios have been considered. The actual burst pressure can be as much as 48% lower than the nominal for single layer vessels and 12% less for vessels with two layers.

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Figure 3: Effect of manufacturing tolerances on the burst pressure of pressure vessel with one ply and the thickness ratio of $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.01$ (Case 1).

Figure 4: Effect of manufacturing tolerances on the burst pressure of pressure vessel with one ply and the thickness ratio of $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.1$ (Case 1).

Figure 5: Effect of manufacturing tolerances on the burst pressure of pressure vessel with two layers and the thickness ratio of $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.01$ (Case 1).

Figure 6: Effect of manufacturing tolerances on the burst pressure of pressure vessel with two layers and the thickness ratio of $R_{ext}/R_{int} = 1.1$ (Case 1).